

Relationship between weed dry weight and rice grain yield under upland condition. Parwanipur, India, 1988.

yield per unit increase in dry weed weight to be between 0.48% (1.4206 g/m²) and 0.23% (0.6929 g/m²), at 99% level of confidence.

The equation developed here could be used to assess yield loss caused by weeds in upland ricefields under conditions similar to those in Parwanipur. □

6% broadleaved weeds.

Of the herbicides and cultural treatments tested, thiobencarb at 1.5 kg ai/ha followed by one hand weeding at

25-30 d after sowing (DAS) gave the highest yield and net return (see table). Results with butachlor at the same rate and weeding schedule were similar. □

Weed control in direct sown rice cultivar (MW10) under rainfed upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, MP, India, 1984-86.^a

Treatment	Formulation	Rate applied (kg ai/ha)	Yield (t/ha)				Gross return (\$)	Cost of treatment (\$)	Net return (\$)
			1984	1985	1986	Mean			
Thiobencarb (saturon)	50 EC	2.0	3.5	1.2	0.8	1.8	185	25	160
Thiobencarb plus one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.7	2.8	2.2	2.9	288	35	253
Butachlor (Delchlor)	50 EC	2.0	2.9	1.0	1.0	1.6	164	26	138
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	3.1	3.4	2.0	2.8	285	40	247
Butachlor (Machete)	50 EC	2.0	2.6	0.7	1.0	1.4	141	25	116
Butachlor with one hand weeding at 25-30 DAS	50 EC	1.5	2.7	2.8	2.0	2.5	251	40	211
Pendimethalin	30 EC	1.5	2.4	0.8	0.8	1.4	138	30	108
Hand weeding twice at 20 and 40 DAS			3.4	3.00	1.7	2.7	271	47	224
Weed-free check			3.2	3.1	2.4	2.9	290	67	223
Nonweeded control			1.3	0.8	0.4	0.8	83	00	83
Experiment mean			2.9	2.0	1.6	2.2			
LSD (0.05)			0.5	0.10	0.5				

^aRice \$100.00/t, thiobencarb \$6.00/liter, Delchlor \$6.34/liter, Machete \$6.34/liter, pendimethalin \$5.93, labor charges \$0.67/d, labor required for 2 weedings (40 + 30 DAS) and for weed-free check (40 + 30 + 20 + 10 DAS) in man-days/ha.

Water management

Weed control in direct seeded rice under upland conditions of Chhattisgarh, India

R. Singh and S. K. Shrivastava, *Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwa Vidyalaya (IGKV), College of Agriculture, Raipur 492012, Madhya Pradesh (MP), India*

We evaluated herbicides for effective and economical control of weeds in direct seeded rice under upland conditions. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. MW10 was the test variety.

The dominant weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *Cyperus rotundus*, *Setaria glauca*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Eclipta alba*, *Alternanthera* spp., and *Commelina* spp. The weed population included 65% grasses, 29% sedges, and

Effect of submergence depth on rice yield and water percolation and nitrogen leaching in sandy clay loam soils

T. Ramalingam, C. Ramaswami, T. Lakshminarayanan, and P. Singaravelu, *Soil and Water Management Research Institute, Thanjavur, India*

We measured the effect of different submergence depths on rice yield, water percolation, and nitrogen leaching in the sandy clay loam (Typic Haplustalf) soils of Thanjavur District. The experimental field had neutral soil reaction and low organic matter content (0.51%). Soil had 20% clay, 3% silt, 13% coarse sand, 63% fine sand with low CEC (9.7 meq/100 g) and exchangeable bases.

The experiment was repeated in two seasons--kharif (Jun-Oct) and rabi

(Oct-Jan)--for 3 yr (1985-87). Water depths were 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 cm, maintained by irrigating the 6- × 5-m plots daily.

Loss of water to percolation was measured in 20-cm-diameter, 30-cm-high metal rings covered by polythene sheets. Percolation loss was measured daily from 8 d after planting to 15 d before harvest.

Leachate collected daily after basal and topdressed prilled urea was analyzed for ammoniacal N using magnesium oxide and for nitrate N using Devarda alloy. Nitrogen loss by leaching was quantified from N concentration in the leachate and amount of water lost by percolation.

Daily topping with 2.5 or 5.0 cm water significantly increased yield compared to 7.5 cm water depth during the dry season. Percolation loss increased with depth of submergence